

Conductance Studies in Multicomponent Solutions Involving Electrolytes

R. L. BLOKHRA*, Y. P. SEHGAL and SATISH KUMAR

Department of Chemistry, Himachal Pradesh University, Simla-171 005

Manuscript received 20 November 1979, revised 25 March 1980, accepted 21 May 1980

Electrical conductance, in water, determined at 30°, have been used to calculate activity coefficient and dissociation constants in multicomponent solutions. Electrical conductance at infinite dilution have been used as measure of solute-solvent interaction. The activity coefficient is found to increase more rapidly with concentration. Dissociation constant shows that association in the case of lithium chloride is greater than in case of sodium chloride and potassium chloride.

ELECTRICAL conductance have been used as a measure of solute-solvent interaction¹⁻⁶. The solute-solvent interaction that has received a great importance have also been studied from the estimation of properties like molar volume⁷⁻¹¹, free energy of transfer¹²⁻¹⁴ and viscosity¹⁵⁻¹⁹. Literature is full of such studies as single component solutions in water but investigations in multicomponent solutions involving mixed solvent is scanty. Recently Padova *et al*²⁰ have determined activity coefficients in aqueous quaternary system NaCl-KCl-MgCl₂ from isopiestic measurements at 25°. Concentrated solutions 0.2 M-0.8 M have been used for investigation. Equivalent conductance at infinite dilution being calculated from equation due to Robinson and Stokes²⁷. The object of study is to investigate solute-solvent interaction in multicomponent solutions that play important role in physiological processes and cell equilibria in both plants and animals.

Experimental

Materials: Water needed for preparation of various solutions was prepared by distilling thrice, over alkaline KMnO₄. The specific conductance of water thus prepared was 1.3×10^{-6} ohm⁻¹cm⁻¹. Electrolytes viz., potassium and sodium chloride were of AnalaR grade and were used without further purification. Lithium chloride (BDH) was purified by recrystallising from water and dried for 24 hours at 130° in an oven. Every electrolyte was kept over P₂O₅ in vacuum desiccator before use.

Procedure: All solutions were made by weight and conversion of molality to molarity was carried out by expression²². Conductance²³ and density²⁴ measurements were carried out by methods described in our earlier publications. All measurements made in thermostat have fluctuation in temperature less than $\pm 0.05^\circ$. The standard deviation in density and conductance measurements are ± 0.000011 gm. cm⁻³ and ± 0.04 ohm⁻¹cm²mol⁻¹ respectively.

Results and Discussion

Equivalent conductance at infinite dilution was calculated from the equation due to Robinson and Stokes²⁷.

$$\Lambda = \Lambda_0 - \left[\frac{az_1z_2q\Delta_0}{1+q} + b(z_1+z_2) \right] \frac{I^{\frac{1}{2}}}{1+Ba^\circ I^{\frac{1}{2}}} \dots (1)$$

Here Λ = Equivalent conductance of solution

Λ_0 = Equivalent conductance at infinite dilution

z_1, z_2 = Charge no. of ions (cation and anion)

a, b = Constants

I = Total ionic strength

a° = Closest distance of approach

B = Constant having value 0.33 approx. at 30°.

The value of Λ_0 was determined from the intercept of plot Λ versus $I^{\frac{1}{2}}/1+Ba^\circ I^{\frac{1}{2}}$. The constant a° was arbitrarily adjusted to give the best fit. The value varied from 3-5 Å.

The value of dissociation constant suggests that there is partial association. The values of Λ_0 were also calculated from Owen's plots²⁸. The approximate value being taken from Λ versus $\sqrt{C}$ plots.

The values of limiting equivalent conductance determined from the two methods is recorded in Table 1 alongwith the value of dissociation constant.

The order of magnitude of Λ_0 for varied solutions is as follows :

But the value of dissociation constant shows that

TABLE 1—LIMITING EQUIVALENT CONDUCTANCE AND DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS FOR MULTICOMPONENT SOLUTIONS AT 30°C

System	Λ_0 (Robinson and Stokes) (ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)	Λ_0 (Owen's) (ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)	K Dissociation Constant × 10
0.01 M KCl + NaCl(C)	121.1	127.9	3.47
0.01 M KCl + LiCl(C)	119.5	113.9	3.69
0.01 M LiCl + KCl(C)	173.2	172.0	1.95
0.01 M LiCl + NaCl(C)	122.5	124.4	3.62
0.01 M NaCl + KCl(C)	175.8	170.2	0.50
0.01 M NaCl + LiCl(C)	118.5	112.5	0.29
0.01 M LiCl + 0.01 M NaCl + KCl(C)	180.1	190.0	0.48
0.01 M KCl + 0.01 M LiCl + NaCl(C)	134.2	139.5	1.12
0.01 M KCl + 0.01 M NaCl + LiCl(C)	132.0	123.2	0.17

the order of association is :

Li⁺ ion being highly hydrated and showing more association than others, is less mobile and hence shows less equivalent conductance at infinite dilution than others. KCl shows more association than NaCl, the greater limiting equivalent conductance may be due to the greater mobility of K⁺. Since Λ_0 have been regarded as measure²⁷ of solute-solvent interaction, the greater value in a particular solvent may therefore be interpreted in terms of greater ion-solvent interactions. Limiting equivalent conductance was used to calculate the degree of dissociation of varied solutions. The activity coefficient was then calculated using equation²⁷ :

$$-\log f = \frac{A(\sqrt{\alpha C})}{1 + B(\sqrt{\alpha C})} \quad \dots (2)$$

where f = activity coefficient

α = degree of dissociation

C = molar concentration

a = closest distance of approach

A and B are constants.

The value of A and B at 30° was determined from plots A versus temperature and B versus temperature respectively as they increase linearly with temperature²⁸.

Ignoring the small difference between f and γ , the f value was used to calculate the dissociation constant by equation²⁷ :

$$K = \frac{\alpha^2 \gamma^2 C}{(1 - \alpha)} \quad \dots (3)$$

Table 2 shows the values of activity coefficient for different solutions and we find that the value of activity coefficient increases with concentration,

Further the value of activity coefficient has the following order :

The reasons for this order may be the order of association.

TABLE 2—ACTIVITY COEFFICIENT VALUES FOR DIFFERENT SOLUTIONS OF MULTICOMPONENT SYSTEMS AT 30°C

Molarity (× 10³ (mol. l⁻¹)) Activity Coefficient (f)

Solute : NaCl Solvent : 0.01 M KCl in water	
9.932	0.240
19.848	0.297
29.724	0.331
39.599	0.356
58.994	0.390
78.938	0.413

Solute : LiCl Solvent : 0.01 M KCl in water	
9.928	0.223
19.811	0.267
29.651	0.299
39.471	0.322
58.919	0.343
78.169	0.360

Solute : KCl Solvent : 0.01 M LiCl in water	
9.955	0.234
29.696	0.320
39.470	0.345
58.703	0.373
78.044	0.394

Solute : NaCl Solvent : 0.01 M LiCl in water	
19.931	0.295
29.800	0.330
39.579	0.357
59.194	0.389
78.630	0.412

Solute : KCl Solvent : 0.01 M NaCl in water	
19.803	0.277
29.612	0.306
39.379	0.325
58.801	0.353
77.986	0.375

(Table 2 Contd.)

Solute : LiCl	
Solvent : 0.01 M NaCl in water	
9.932	0.220
29.633	0.293
39.474	0.312
58.971	0.336
78.170	0.353
Solute : KCl	
Solvent : 0.01 M LiCl + 0.01 M NaCl in water	
19.859	0.277
29.683	0.298
39.471	0.323
58.908	0.360
78.119	0.371
Solute : NaCl	
Solvent : 0.01 M KCl + 0.01 M LiCl in water	
19.917	0.285
29.781	0.318
39.632	0.337
59.203	0.368
78.651	0.389
Solute : LiCl	
Solvent : 0.01 M NaCl + 0.01 M KCl in water	
9.955	0.218
19.857	0.263
29.706	0.287
39.519	0.304
58.968	0.330
78.287	0.346

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (Satish Kumar) is thankful to CSIR, New Delhi for award of JRF in the scheme.

References

1. P. BRUNO, M. DELLA MONICA and E. RIGHETTI, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1973, **77**, 1258.
2. S. BHANDARI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 88.
3. U. MEYER, V. GUTMAN and A. LODZINSKA, *Montash.*, 1973, **104**, 1045.
4. D. F. EVANS, J. A. NADAS and M. A. MATEICH, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1971, **75**, 1708.
5. N. P. YAO and D. H. BENNION, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1971, **118**, 1097.
6. N. P. ZIPP, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1973, **77**, 718.
7. F. J. MILLERO, *Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **71**, 147.
8. G. K. WARD and F. J. MILLERO, *J. Soln. Chem.*, 1974, **3**, 431.
9. RAM GOPAL and M. A. SIDDIQI, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, **72**, 1814.
10. H. L. WELLES and R. E. INDSTORM, *J. Soln. Chem.*, 1976, **5**, 155.
11. J. M. MCDOWALL and C. A. VINCENT, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. I*, 1974, **70**, 1862.
12. K. K. KUNDU and M. N. DAS, *J. Phys. Chem. Electrochim. Acta*, 1973, **18**, 95.
13. U. SEN, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. I*, 1973, 2006.
14. H. P. BENNETTO and M. M. SPITZER, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. I*, 1973, 1492.
15. P. B. DAS, *Curr. Sci.*, 1975, **44**, 887.
16. R. L. BLOKHRA and Y. P. SEHGAL, *J. Soln. Chem.*, 1976, **5**, 499.
17. D. ENGLAND and G. PILLING, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1972, **76**, 1902.
18. C. F. MATTINA and R. M. FUOSS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1975, **79**, 1604.
19. B. N. PRASAD and M. M. AGARWAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, **14A**, 343.
20. J. PADOVA and D. SAAD, *J. Soln. Chem.*, 1977, **6**, 57.
21. C. W. DAVIES, "Ion Association", Butterworths, London, 1962, 20.
22. D. P. SHOENMAKER and C. W. GARLAND, "Experiments in Physical Chemistry", McGraw Hill, New York, 1967, 130.
23. R. L. BLOKHRA, Y. P. SEHGAL and V. P. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 505.
24. R. L. BLOKHRA and Y. P. SEHGAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, **12**, 998.
25. B. B. OWEN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 1393.
26. S. GLASSTONE, "An Introduction to Electrochemistry", Van Nostrand Reinhold Company, New York, 1942, 60.
27. R. A. ROBINSON and R. H. STOKES, "Electrolyte Solutions", Butterworths, London, 1970, 407.
28. D. A. MACINNIS, "The Principles of Electrochemistry", Dover Publications, Inc., New York, 144.